

SHORT COMMUNICATION

***Mezium americanum* (Laporte de Castelnau, 1840), a new synonym of *Mezium sulcatum* (Fabricius, 1781) (Coleoptera: Ptinidae, Gibbiinae, Meziini)**

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ABSTRACT

Synonymy of two species of the genus *Mezium* Curtis has been established: *M. sulcatum* (F.) proved taxonomically identical to *M. americanum* (Laporte). For *Mezium hirticolle* (Laporte) the status has changed.

Keywords: entomology, taxonomy, nomenclature, Coleoptera, Ptinidae, Gibbiinae, Meziini, new synonym, new status

After the revision of the two type specimens from the collection of J. Ch. Fabricius (Natural History Museum in London) (Figs 1-2) it was proven that *Ptinus sulcatus* Fabricius, 1781 is an older synonym of *Gibbium americanum* Laporte de Castelnau, 1840. In that case, *Mezium hirticolle* (Laporte) received a new status.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Figs 1-2. The type specimen of *Ptinus sulcatus* Fabricius, 1781;
1 – the label under specimens; 2 – the shape of pronotum and the „collar” of elytra.

Below is given the list of synonyms of *Mezium sulcatum* (F.) and *M. hirticolle* (Laporte) with their geographical distribution and a shape of the bodies (Figs 3-4):

Mezium sulcatum (Fabricius, 1781), Fig. 3.

Ptinus Sulcatus Fabricius, 1781: 73

Gibbium americanum Castelnau de Laporte, 1840: 297 **syn. nov.**

Gibbium nitidipenne Germain, 1856: 395

Mezium arachnoides Desbrochers des Loges, 1875: 50

Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. A body of *Mezium sulcatum* (F.), dorsal view.

Geographical distribution: Palearctic element, probably originated in the Canary Islands. The species was introduced with dry plant materials or excrement of herbivores to various countries of the world.

Mezium hirticolle (Castelnau de Laporte, 1840), Fig. 4., **stat. nov.**

Gibbium hirticolle Castelnau de Laporte, 1840: 297

Mezium cristatum Boheman, 1858: 86

Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. A body of *Mezium hirticolle* (Laporte), dorsal view.

Geographical distribution: Palearctic element, probably originated in the Canary Islands. The species was sporadically introduced with dry plant materials or excrement of herbivores to the continental part of Europe and South America.

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